

Synthesis of Possible Antifertility Compounds. Part I. Synthesis of α -Cinnamoyl Derivatives of Coumarones

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2-Cinnamoyl and *para*-substituted cinnamoyl derivatives of 3-methylbenzofurans have been prepared with a view to testing their antifertility activity.

After demonstration of the estrogenic activity in oxygen heterocyclic compounds, such as coumarins¹, isoflavens, and isoflavones²⁻³, several 2-arylbenzofurans and related compounds were synthesised⁴. A *p*-OH group in the 2-aryl substituent was found to be an essential requirement for estrogenic activity as in the isoflavone² and the coumarin group. Derivatives of 3,4-diphenylcoumarin have recently been prepared⁵ and some of them have been found to possess marked antifertility activity. In view of these observations it was considered worthwhile to undertake the synthesis of a number of 2, 3-di-substituted benzofurans (I) with a 2-cinnamoyl moiety.

The synthesis was accomplished along the following route:

The methyl-substituted hydroxyketone failed to provide any solid product by the usual procedure and hence anhydrous conditions were applied for the reaction.

*EXPERIMENTAL

2-Acetyl-3-methyl-substituted Benzofurans: Method (A).—The potassium salt of *O*-hydroxyacetophenone (0.1 *M*), obtained from an appropriate ketone (0.1 *M*) and ethanolic

* All m.p.s are uncorrected.

1. Gley *et al.*, *Compt. rend. soc. biol.*, 1945, 139, 1058; *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1940, 271.

2. Bradbury and White, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 3447; 1953, 871.

3. Pope *et al.*, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1953, 1092; 1954, 1019; Bose and Chandran, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1954, 13B, 888.

4. Bisagni *et al.* *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 3688; 3093; Buu-Hoï *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1957, 625.

5. Londale *et al.*, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1955, 8, 725.

KOH (0.125 *M*), was heated with EtOH (50 ml) till it dissolved. Redistilled bromoacetone (0.1 *M*) was slowly added when a vigorous reaction took place. When the reaction had subsided, the reaction mixture was diluted with an equal volume of water and after removal of the ethanol it was extracted with ether. The extract was washed with water till free of the unchanged bromoacetone, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, and the ether distilled; the solid obtained was recrystallised from ethanol.

Method (B).—The method was essentially the same except the following modification: To the dried potassium salt of ketone bromoacetone was added dropwise with constant shaking and the mixture was kept at the room temperature for additional 2 hours and then extracted with ether after addition of water. Subsequent procedure was as in method (A). In the case of 2-acetyl-3, 7-dimethylbenzofuran a reddish syrupy liquid was obtained which on keeping for nearly 72 hr. solidified to yellow crystals. The yield, m.p. of benzofurans, and analyses of their semicarbazones and oximes are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

R.	M.P.	Method.	Yield.	*Derivative.	M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
							Found.	Reqd.
5-Cl	116°	A	60%	S	231-32°	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₃ Cl	15.36	15.81
				O	148-49°	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₂ NCl	6.09	6.26
7-Cl	102°	A	62	S	228°	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₃ Cl	15.42	15.81
				O	170°	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₂ NCl	6.03	6.26
5-Me	60°	B	55	S	245°	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₃	17.03	17.13
				O	137°	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ O ₂ N	6.42	6.80
7-Me	52°	B	58	S	218°	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₃	17.00	17.13
				O	127°	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ O ₂ N	6.31	6.89

*S and O denote, respectively, semicarbazone and oxime.

2-Cinnamoyl-3-methylbenzofurans.—A mixture of 2-acetyl-3-methyl-substituted benzofuran (0.001 *M*), aromatic aldehyde (0.001 *M*), EtOH (10 ml), and HCl (2-3 drops, conc.) was refluxed for 10-12 hr. and subsequently kept in an ice-chest overnight. The crystals obtained were filtered and recrystallised from ethanol. The products of condensation of benzofurans with various aldehydes, m.p., yield, and analyses of their semicarbazones are recorded in Table II,

TABLE II
(Vide structure I)

R'.	M.P.	Yield.	*M.P.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.
R = 5-Cl.						
H	125°	65%	233°	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₃ Cl	11.39	11.37
4'-OH	160°	65	240°	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	11.11	11.36
4'-OMe	169°	73	237°	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	10.83	10.94
4'-OH	120°	67	221-22°	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₃ Cl	10.11	10.51
5'-OMe	..					
R = 7-Cl.						
H	140°	65	231°	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₃ Cl	11.46	11.67
4'-OH	130°	66	235-36°	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	11.03	11.36
4'-OMe	151°	65	200°	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	10.30	10.94
4'-OH	161°	68	237°	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₃ Cl	10.46	10.51
5'-OMe						
R = 5-Me.						
H	146°	66	235°	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₃	12.35	12.60
4'-OH	167°	72	236°	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₃	11.08	12.02
4'-OMe	122°	70	244°	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₃	11.50	11.56
4'-OH	116°	65°	229°	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₃	10.60	11.07
5'-Me						
R = 7-Me.						
4'-OMe	122°	70	161°	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₃ N ₃	11.23	11.56
4'-OH	103°	66	230	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₃	10.73	11.07
5'-OMe	..	..	..	..	..	..
4'-Cl	123°	63	205°	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₃ Cl	11.02	11.42

* Refers to semicarbazones.

Semicarbazones and oximes were obtained by the usual method.

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